

Brief Research Report

Poor Male Students' Enrolment into Home Economics and Related Programmes in Tertiary Institutions in Anambra State, Nigeria

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Abstract: The study looked at the issue of poor male students' enrollment into Home Economics and related programmes in tertiary institutions in Anambra State, Nigeria. It adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population for this study comprised of all the (regular) undergraduate students in the Home Economics related programmes in the five tertiary institutions in Anambra State. The population is two hundred and six (206) students. Instrument used for the study was a structured 4-point questionnaire. The instrument's validity was ensured through consulting experts in Home Economics and Measurement and Evaluation fields in, Nwafor Orizu College of Education, Nsugbe. The reliability of the instrument was established through a test re-test procedure and correlated to yield a coefficient of 0.81. Data for this study was collected primarily by the researchers. The data were analyzed with arithmetic mean and standard deviation. From the results, it was identified that the causes of poor male student enrollment revolve around societal stereotypes, limited awareness of the subject's scope, inadequate promotional efforts; among others. Educational outreach and awareness, deconstructing gender stereotypes, parental and community engagement, were suggested as strategies to improve male students enrolment. Based on findings, the researchers recommend a curriculum adjustment and more inclusive educational environment and mindset that will showcase Home Economics as a field suitable for all, regardless of gender.

Keywords: Enrolment, Home Economics, Male students, Strategies, Tertiary institutions

1. Introduction

Home Economics as a unique and dynamic field of study has its central theme hinged on the improvement of the lives of individuals (male and female), families and society. It draws knowledge from many disciplines including the Sciences and Humanities in order to fulfill its objectives. Home Economics is that field of study that is concerned with developing and building the individual and family life by providing functional knowledge and skills (Baiden, et al., 2022). Oranu (2014) opines that Home Economics is a means through which an individual maybe led to a stronger growth and development. Thus, enabling him/her to take responsibilities in the family and society. Home Economics involves the study of all the elements of family living, individual development and interpersonal relations (Ngride, 2013). Home Economics is an academic discipline that combines all aspects of social and natural sciences. It includes how individuals develop and function in family, work and community settings and how they relate to their physical, social, emotional and intellectual environment. Uzoka (2013) define Home Economics as a way of living. It is a trade as well as a profession based on how one looks at it.

Home Economics as a field of formal study covers a vast area of knowledge including consumer education, institutional management, interior design, home furnishing, cleaning, handicrafts, sewing, clothing and textiles, commercial cooking, nutrition, food preservation, child development, managing money, and family relationships. In addition, family management, environmental and drug substance awareness might be also covered along with topics such as fire prevention and safety procedures (Lichtenteen & Ludroig, 2010). These knowledge competencies prepare individuals for a particular field of work to earn a living and also be useful to the society at large. Uzoka (2013), added that Home Economics formally in Nigeria way back in the 18th century by the early missionaries as subjects like Domestic science, cookery, needle work, homecraft. Prior to this time, Home Economics had been traditionally and informally taught to girls and mothers by much elderly women within their immediate environment either through apprenticeship or direct counseling by close relatives depending on the training circumstances. In 1927, Queens Colleges, Lagos became the first indigenous school in Nigeria to start Home Economics in the formal sense. It was also the first school to present the subject to West African Examination Council (WAEC). Historically, Home Economics education has been in the context of the home and household but this has extended in the 21st century to include the wider living environment as it better understand choices and priorities of individuals and families. Today, the subject is taught at all levels of basic education (nursery, primary, secondary schools), and also tertiary institutions as a course (colleges and universities), in vocational schools and adult education centers. In a nutshell, Home Economics is a power house of career opportunities.

Despite the laudable potentials of Home Economics as a course of study, it is rather unfortunate all that may not be fully harnessed by everyone as a result of gender streamlining and prejudice. Observations and researches have shown that there is a serious deficit of male students in Home Economics departments across tertiary institutions in the state. A preliminary survey of male students enrollment into the programme of Home Economics and related subjects in various tertiary institutions in Anambra State indicated a concerning trend of poor male student enrollment in this field. Findings

from Oko Federal Polytechnic, in Anambra State reveals the absence of male student in the 100 level whereas there are only two male student in the 200 level. Similarly, the department of Home Economics in Nwafor Orizu College of Education Nsugbe, only recorded an unprecedented intake of a single male student in the current academic year (2023/2024). Anambra State Polytechnic Mgbakwu have no male student yet. This gender disparity in male enrolment into Home Economics and related courses raises serious concerns and calls for urgent actions. This shows that there are very few males in the discipline and the gains of Home Economics are yet to be fully enjoyed by the male gender as there is very low male students' enrolment in the course. Page | 256

According to Yi and Dural-Covelal (2021), student enrolment is the art of signing up for school and/or specific classes or co-curricular activities at a particular school. It is the process of arranging to attend an institution and specific classes. Student enrolment is a process of ensuring attendance in an educational institution. According to Ahmedi et al. (2023), student enrolment is the process by which individuals formally register and become affiliated with educational institutions such as a school, college, or university or pursue academic programs or courses. It involves, submitting necessary documents, personal information's and after payment of tuition fees. This term may also describe the number of students that current attend a school or a course. Student enrolment signifies a commitment to participate in educational activities access resources, and engage in learning experience offered by the institution. Mehboob, Shah and Phutin (2013) state that students enroll into college based on several criteria including academic quality, facilities, campus surroundings and personal characteristics. Also, income affects the choice of student in enrolment into higher educational institutions (Ming, 2010). In addition to these factors, the decisions of the students to enrol in any course considers the recognition of the academic degree or the program nationally or internationally, the degree flexibility, the diversity of courses and the flexibility of entry requirements. Students then select courses to take through the schools' student information services. Going by these definitions of enrolment, there is a very low male student enrolment in Home Economics Department in Tertiary Institutions across the state. This may be as a result of lack of interest, prejudice, gender streamlining and a host of other factors as Saylor and Alexandra (2010) explained that low enrolment can be due to lack of students' interest in school, school failures, inability to do school work, that is poor study habits, lack of participation in curricular activities, financial cost of attending school, low economic status of parents, low educational level of parents and lack of parental interest on children's schooling, to attraction of outside employment. As a related statistical indicator the school enrolment rate is defined as the ratio of official school age (Hampton, Dawkins, Patrick, O'Leary-Kelley, Onglengco and Stobbe, 2022). School enrolment rate term the basis for a variety of other educational indicators, such as the mean years of schooling and expected years of schooling which measures the duration an individual is enrolled in school.

The issue of poor male students' enrollment in Home Economics has caused negative economic development and resulted to wasted talents and incompetent labour force in most parts of Nigeria (Ojih, Esiekpe & Okafor, 2016). This is evidenced by economic and social stagnation in some career fields and unavailability of male Home Economics programme. Process of change brought by poor male

students' enrollment into Home Economics is so problematic that it gives rise to major socio-economic challenges which can have disruptive effects on traditional lifestyles, morals, religious, beliefs and everyday patterns without clear new values (Wamichwe, et al., 2017). To buttress this fact researches such as Neequaye, Darkwa and Amu (2014), which stated that, in Nigeria, Home Economics education is dominated by females with less than 5% male enrolment, have proven that the low male students enrolment in Home Economics create a problem as the diverse perspectives, creating and innovations, a balanced gender involvement ought to bring has been missing. The female-biased nature of Home Economics education in Nigeria as noted by Abruquah (2012) can be traced to the way and manner the programme was introduced into the formal education system. These authors further stated that from the very beginning the content, structure and scope of Home Economics in Nigeria were limited to traditional feminine roles and boys were discouraged from performing these perceived female roles both in school and at home. And as such, girls were offered the Home Economics course and boys took other courses, such as the sciences and the technical courses and the pattern has persisted to this day (Abruquah, 2012). The society through stereotypes and perspectives has made Home Economics a feminine course. Therefore, the society tend to have lots of male graduate from other disciplines and little or none from Home Economics education, thereby bringing an increase to female Home Economics teachers. Raabe, Boda and Standtfield (2019) says that students' tends to shy away from majority in Home Economics program for fear for having difficulty securing employment when they graduate. It is clear that Home Economics has a gender divide. More men than women enroll in courses related to science, agriculture, business and technology.

Azubuike (2012) highlighted that Home Economics is viewed by male as a programme related to the home, as it deals with various food preparations and servings, as well as decorating the home and its surroundings, manufacturing clothing as well as child care and education. As a result, because it is deemed a feminine course and not appropriate for male students. Thus, students view Home Economics as a course that makes one a servant rather than a master, and this perception persists despite being a misconception. Lack of male role models in Home Economics is quite problematic as Arubayi (2009), indicated that discussions in the field tend to be dominated by a single perspective, typically female-oriented. This lack of diversity limits the scope of Home Economics, making it less appealing to a broader audience, including males. Again, in a research conducted by Baiden, et al. (2022), which highlighted that absence of males in the study discipline leads to a dearth of male participation in culinary arts and goes on to perpetuate gender stereotypes and further contribute to the lack of diverse perspectives in the field. The scarcity of male role models in Home Economics according to Eric, Adamu and Ogochukwu (2019), causes prospective male students to often struggle to identify with successful male figures in Home Economics. This lack of representation can undermine enrolment into the field. Additionally, poor quality of schools, inadequate infrastructures and lack of male lecturers, as perceived by male students, tend to result to poor enrolment of male students into Home Economics and related courses. Negative attitude of students towards Home Economics as a feminine course and other importance aspect include curriculum size, student teacher ratio, infrastructure, lack of finance and excess content, and some parents do not encourage their male

children to enroll into Home Economics department because they view it as female oriented course.

Furthermore, Uwameige (2015) highlighted factors such as negative attitude of parents, poor institutional funding, and low awareness to the relevance of the course to be among the courses of the poor male students' enrolment experience in Home Economics. Ogunmosin, Akinyotu, and Orisamika (2021) noted that despite the laudable qualities of Home Economics Education parents are yet to send their sons to do the course. These authors further stated that an all-inclusive curricular, deconstructing gender stereotypes, diversification of role models community and parental engagement can help in curbing these problems. This study therefore, intends to systemically identify the causes and achievable strategies towards ameliorating the issue of poor male student enrolment into Home Economics and related programmes in tertiary institutions in Anambra State.

1.1. Statement of Problem

A preliminary survey of male students enrollment into the programme of Home Economics and related subjects in various tertiary institutions in Anambra State indicated a concerning trend of poor male student enrollment in this field. Findings from Oko Federal Polytechnic, in Anambra State revealed the absence of male students in the 100 level whereas there are only two male students in the 200 level. Similarly, the department of Home Economics and hospitality management in Nwafor Orizu College of Education Nsugbe, and Anambra State Polytechnic Mgbakwu are no better. This gender disparity in students' enrolment into Home Economics and related courses raises several concerns and calls for serious investigation on the causes and possible solutions.

1.2. Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of this research is to examine the issue of poor male enrolment into Home Economics and related courses in tertiary institutions identify the causes and solutions to their problems. Specific purpose is to:

- (a) Causes of poor male student enrollment into Home Economics and related programme in tertiary institutions in Anambra State.
- (b) Effects of poor male student enrollment into Home Economics and related programme in tertiary institutions in Anambra State.
- (c) Strategies towards enhancing male student enrollment into Home Economics.

1.3. Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- (a) What are the causes of poor male students' enrollment into Home Economics and related programmes in tertiary institutions in Anambra State?
- (b) What are the effects of poor male students' enrollment into Home Economics and related programmes in tertiary institutions in Anambra State?
- (c) What strategies can be adopted towards enhancing poor male students' enrollment into Home Economics and related programmes in tertiary institutions in Anambra State?

1.4. Theoretical Framework of the Study

1.4.1. Social Role Theory

Eagly's (1987) social role theory argues that widely shared gender stereotypes develop from the

gender division of labor that characterizes a society. In western societies, men's greater participation in paid positions of higher power and status and the disproportionate assignment of nurturing roles to women have created stereotypes that associate agency with men and communion with women. In addition, the gendered division of labor gives men and women differentiated skills. When gender stereotypes are salient in a group because of a mixed sex membership or a task or context that is culturally associated with one gender, stereotypes shape behavior directly through the expectations members form for one another's behaviours. Social role theory has a broad scope that applies to interaction in all contexts and addresses assertive, power related behaviors as well as supportive or affective behaviors. This theory is linked to the current study as societal role definition is one of the major factors that have influenced male students' enrolment into Home Economics and related disciplines in tertiary institutions in Anambra state.

1.4.2. The Consumer Choice Theory

The theory of consumer choice is the branch of microeconomics that relates preferences to consumption expenditures and to consumer demand curves. It analyzes how consumers maximize the desirability of their consumption (as measured by their preferences subject to limitations on their expenditures), by maximizing utility subject to a consumer budget constraint. Factors influencing consumers' evaluation of the utility of goods include: income level, cultural factors, product information and physio-psychological factors. Consumer choice theory is a hypothesis about why people buy things. It considers three basic assumptions which are; the utility maximization, the principle of non-satiation and the law of decreasing marginal utility. Consumer choice theory has influenced everything from government policy to corporate advertising to academia. It is linked to this study as individual needs, preferences and satisfaction are considered during enrolment.

1.4.3. The Human Capital Theory

In the 1960s, economists Gary Becker and Theodore Schultz pointed out that education and training were investments that could add to productivity. As the world accumulated more and more physical capital, the opportunity cost of going to school declined. Education became an increasingly important component of the workforce. The term was also adopted by corporate finance and became part of intellectual capital, and more broadly as human capital. Intellectual and human capital are treated as renewable sources of productivity. Organizations try to cultivate these sources, hoping for added innovation or creativity. Sometimes, a business problem requires more than just new machines or more money. Human capital theory is about the idea of humans increasing their productivity and efficiency through a greater focus on education and training. Human capital according to Emeka and Udaya (2021), is the study of human resources. It talks about the development of economic value from how we function as a society. Investments in the physical means of business, like machinery or technology creates room for increased productivity and profits whereas an investment in the human capital – through education and training allows growth - measured through staff's abilities, values, and skill set. This will increase business productivity, and in time, revenue, and brand-name. These qualities might be classed as tangible. But through consistency, it can increase financial performance and talent. Human capital can include qualities like: Education, communication skills, people

management, workplace training, problem solving skills, physical, mental, and emotional wellbeing. The human capital theory is related to the current study as Home Economics is viewed by scholars such as Emeka and Udaya (2021) to be a hub for human capital development.

2. Materials and Methods

1.1. Design for the Study

The research design used for this work is descriptive survey design. Descriptive survey design is aimed at collecting data on and describing a systematic manner, the characteristics, features or facts about a given population. This design is considered suitable because only a part of the population is studied and findings from this are expected to be generalized to the entire population.

2.1.1. Ethics Statement

Proper research ethics were upheld in the course of the study. Ethical approval was gotten from the Department of Home Economics Education, Nwafor Orizu College of Education Nsugbe. Respondents were not coerced to respond and their right to confidentiality was optimally observed.

2.2. Area of the Study

The study was conducted in tertiary institutions in Anambra State that offer Home Economics and related programmes. The institutions include Anambra State Polytechnic Mgbakwu, Federal Polytechnic Oko and Nwafor Orizu College of Education Nsugbe. Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka, Federal College of Education (Technical) Umunze is presently located in Umunze, headquarters of Orumba South Local Government Area of Anambra State. Presently academic work is going on both at the temporary and permanent sites. Umunze is perhaps unique in that, it is so centrally located, that is within easy reach of the most cities as Onitsha, Aba, Awka, Owerri, Enugu, Nnewi, Umuahia and Asaba. Mgbakwu is a village located in Awka North Local Government Area in Anambra State. Oko town is an Igbo speaking town in South Eastern Nigeria. It is one of the 16 towns that make up the geopolitical area called Orumba North Local Government Area of Anambra State. Nwafor Orizu College of Education is in Nsugbe town in Anambra East Local Government Area, Anambra State and is bounded on the North by Anambra Omambala River, on the South by Nkwelle-Ezunaka town, on the West by Onitsha town and on the East by Umueri town. Nsugbe people are predominantly farmers and some of the inhabitants also do quarry business. Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka also called Unizik or NAU in short is a Federal University in Nigeria. It consists of two campuses in Anambra State. It's main campus is in Awka, while it's other campus is in Nnewi. There are also other campuses of Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, these include Agulu in Aniocha Local Government Area and Ifite-Ogwuari in Anyamelum Local Government Area in Anambra State.

2.3. Population and Sample

The population for this study comprised of all the full time undergraduate students in the Home Economics related programmes in the five tertiary institutions in Anambra State. The population is two hundred and six (206) (see Table 1).

Table 1: List of five tertiary institutions in Anambra State

S/N	Institution	Programme	Population Size
1	Anambra State Polytechnic Mgbakwu	Human Nutrition and Dietitian	5
		Food Science (Agric department)	8
2	Federal Polytechnic Oko	Home Economics	16
		Food Technology Hospitality Management	42
3	Nwafor Orizu College of Education, Nsugbe	Home Economics and Hospitality Management	33
4	Federal College of Education Umunze	Home Economics	32
5	Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka	Food Science and Technology	70
			206

Since the target population was of a manageable size, the entire population was used in carrying out the study, therefore no sampling was done, making the sample size a total of 206 respondents

2.4. Instrument for Data Collection and Study Procedure

Instrument used for the study was a structured 4-point questionnaire. Questionnaire was considered for an appropriate instrument for a descriptive survey research question for the study. The instrument was divided into four sections (A, B, C and D). Section A contains the instrument and personal data of the respondents while Section B, C and D consisted of 3 part questions of 30 research questions that elicited responses from the respondents. The researcher used four point scale of Strongly Agreed (SA = 4 points), Agree (A = 3 points), Disagreed (D = 2 points), Strongly Disagree (SD = 1 point). The respondents were to tick the accurate options as applicable to them. Questionnaire is considered as a appropriate instrument for descriptive survey design research question for the study. The overall theme of the questions was on issue of poor male students' enrolment into Home Economics program into tertiary institutions in Anambra State: causes and solution.

2.5. Data Collection Technique

Data for this study was collected primarily. This method helped to collect first information through questionnaire from students in Nwafor Orizu College of Education, Nsugbe. The researcher went round to distribute the questionnaire to them using face to face mode of administration was used to ensure 100% return. 136 copies of questionnaire will be administered to the selected respondents by the researcher. The questionnaire was collected from the respondents almost immediately.

2.6. Data Analysis Technique

The collected data were analyzed the mean and standard deviation.

$$\text{Mean} = \bar{X} = \frac{\sum fx}{N}$$

$$\text{Standard deviation} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum fx}{N} - \left(\frac{\sum fx}{N}\right)^2}$$

Where \bar{X} = mean of response on each questionnaire

F = frequency of each questionnaire item

D = deviation of each scale point from the mean

N = total number of respondents on each questionnaire

Calculation of the design point or cut off means using the likert mode

SA = 4 points

A = 3 points

D = 2 points

SD = 1 point

$$\text{Cut of mean} = \frac{4+3+2+1}{4} = \frac{10}{4} = 2.50$$

3. Results and Discussion

Table 2: Causes of poor male students' enrolment into Home Economics related programme in tertiary institutions in Anambra State.

S/N	Causes	SA	A	D	SD	Total	$\sum FX$	Mean	Std Dev	Decision
1	Gender stereotypes and streamlining discourage male students' enrolment into Home Economics related programmes.	120	60	20	6	206	706	3.43	0.78	Accepted
2	Lack of male role models in the field, causes poor male students enrolment into Home Economics related programmes.	151	29	13	13	206	730	3.54	0.87	Accepted
3	Misunderstanding of subject scope can drive away male students as they feel Home Economics is a female oriented area of study.	172	18	12	4	206	770	3.74	0.65	Accepted
4	Fear of judgement and mockery (prejudice) of male students to enrol into Home Economics related programmes.	169	34	0	3	206	781	3.79	0.50	Accepted
5	False perception of a limited career prospects in Home Economics, causes male students to boycott	89	60	30	10	189	606	3.21	0.89	Accepted

	the area of study.										
6	Inadequate promotional efforts, causes poor male student's enrolment into Home Economics related programmes.	141	25	30	10	206	709	3.44	0.91	Accepted	
7	Peer influence can change the mind of a prospective male to enrol into Home Economics related programmes.	136	40	20	10	206	714	3.47	0.86	Accepted	
8	Lack of funding by the ministry of education for male student enrolment into Home Economics related programmes.	109	49	30	18	206	661	3.21	0.99	Accepted	
9	Insufficient male support from parents and society to enrol into Home Economics programme causes poor male student enrolment into this area.	79	92	25	10	206	652	3.17	0.82	Accepted	

Table 2 above revealed the causes of poor male students enrolment into Home Economics related programme in tertiary institutions in Anambra State. It was revealed that fear of judgement and mockery (prejudice) of male students to enrol into Home Economics related programmes (3.79). The respondents agreed that misunderstanding of subject scope can drive away male students as they feel Home Economics is a female oriented area of study (3.74). Lack of male role models in the field, causes poor male students enrolment into Home Economics related programmes (3.54). On the whole, items 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9 yield a mean scores of 3.43, 3.54, 3.74, 3.79, 3.21, 3.44, 3.47, 3.21 and 3.17 corresponding to standard deviations of 0.78, 0.87, 0.65, 0.50, 0.89, 0.91, 0.86, 0.99 and 0.82 were all accepted respectively.

Table 3: Influence of poor male students' enrolment into Home Economics and related programmes in tertiary institutions.

S/N	Influence	SA	A	D	SD	Total	$\sum FX$	Mean	Std Dev	Decision
10	Limited diversified perspectives in Home Economics related	142	30	9	25	206	701	3.40	1.03	Accepted

	discussions.									
11	Reduced collaboration of potentials as can be seen in mixed gender work.	128	70	0	8	206	730	3.54	0.69	Accepted
12	Missed opportunities for male representation.	99	68	32	7	206	671	3.26	0.84	Accepted
13	Limited male focused research and development in the subject area.	92	79	10	25	206	650	3.16	0.98	Accepted
14	Missed male perspectives in field discussions.	141	30	25	10	206	714	3.47	0.88	Accepted
15	Fewer male role models in the field of Home Economics.	136	40	20	10	206	714	3.47	0.86	Accepted
16	Narrowed / Myopic understanding of family dynamics.	124	62	0	20	206	702	3.41	0.91	Accepted
17	Limited male participation in culinary arts in Nigeria.	151	12	29	14	206	712	3.46	0.97	Accepted
18	Diminished male involvement in child development and rearing.	102	55	30	19	206	652	3.17	0.99	Accepted
19	Impeded progress towards gender equality.	110	30	30	36	206	626	3.04	1.17	Accepted

The result in Table 3 revealed the extent on the influence of poor male student enrolment into Home Economics related programme in tertiary institutions, reduced collaboration of potentials as can be seen in mixed gender work (3.54), fewer male role models in the field of Home Economics (3.47), also, limited male participation in culinary arts in Nigeria (3.46). In all, items 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18 and 19 with mean scores of 3.40, 3.54, 3.26, 3.16, 3.47, 3.47, 3.41, 3.46, 3.17 and 3.04 corresponding to standard deviations of 1.03, 0.69, 0.84, 0.98, 0.88, 0.86, 0.91, 0.97, 0.99 and 1.17 were accepted respectively.

Table 4: Strategies for enhancing male students enrolment into Home Economics related programmes.

S/N	Strategies	SA	A	D	SD	Total	∑FX	Mean	Std Dev	Decision
20	The ministry of Education should implement inclusive	59	25	80	42	206	513	2.49	1.11	Rejected

	and gender balanced curriculum.										
21	Home Economics lectures and students should create awareness campaigns on subject scope through the media and religious groups.	100	48	36	22	206	638	3.10	1.04	Accepted	
22	The course should be updated to encourage more cross-disciplinary connections.	110	36	38	22	206	646	3.14	1.06	Accepted	
23	Government agencies and the Governmental Organisations (NGOs) should offer scholarships for male students to study Home Economics and related courses.	149	27	15	15	206	722	3.50	0.91	Accepted	
24	Tertiary institutions should develop male-focused support networks through, scholarship.	78	80	32	16	206	632	3.07	0.92	Accepted	
25	The ministry of education should address gender bias in education through the media and campaign.	89	67	30	20	206	637	3.09	0.98	Accepted	
26	Tertiary institutions should collaborate with male-oriented clubs in other fields.	136	36	26	10	208	714	3.43	0.89	Accepted	
27	The lecturers should introduces flexible learning formats in teaching Home Economics and it's related areas.	120	48	30	8	206	692	3.36	0.87	Accepted	
28	The ministry of Education and the lecturers should	86	75	24	21	206	638	3.10	0.97	Accepted	

emphasize practical life skills in Home Economics and related fields of study.

The result in Table 4 showed that government agencies and the Governmental Organisations (NGOs) should offer scholarships for male students to study Home Economics and related courses (3.50). The respondents agreed that the ministry of Education should implement inclusive and gender balanced curriculum (3.49). Nevertheless, the respondents disagreed that the ministry of Education should implement inclusive and gender balanced curriculum (2.49). In all, items 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27 and 28 yields mean scores of 3.10, 3.14, 3.50, 3.07, 3.09, 3.43, 3.36 and 3.10 corresponding to standard deviation of 1.04, 1.06, 0.91, 0.92, 0.98, 0.89, 0.87 and 0.97 were accepted, while item 20 yield mean score of 2.49 corresponding to standard deviation of 1.11 is rejected respectively. Page | 266

The implications of the findings are significant, highlighting various aspects that need attention and action to address the challenges related to male enrollment in Home Economics and related programs. The finding that inadequate promotional efforts deter male student enrollment suggests that educational institutions and relevant authorities need to invest in effective marketing strategies. By promoting the benefits, career opportunities, and inclusivity of Home Economics programs, they can attract a more diverse student body. The result indicating limited male participation in culinary arts within Home Economics programs signals the need for curriculum adjustments and a more inclusive approach to teaching. Creating an environment where a culinary art is seen as gender-neutral and suitable for all students is essential.

The finding that the Ministry of Education should address gender bias through media and campaigns highlights the need for governmental support. Policies and initiatives that challenge traditional gender roles and encourage equal participation in educational fields like Home Economics can make a substantial difference. These findings underscore the broader societal issue of gender equality in education. Addressing gender disparities in enrollment can lead to more balanced and diverse perspectives in Home Economics, as well as various related fields. Encouraging male enrollment in Home Economics can have positive economic and social effects. It can contribute to a more skilled workforce, improved family well-being, and a more inclusive society.

The limitations of a study are essential to acknowledge for the sake of transparency and to provide context for the findings. The study has a limited coverage - only tertiary institutions in Anambra State, due to constraints such as time and resources. This limits the extent to which the results can be generalized to the broader population. The data collection method relied primarily on self-reported information obtained through questionnaire. Respondents may not always provide truthful or complete information, which could impact the validity of the results. There may be a tendency for respondents to provide socially desirable responses, particularly when discussing sensitive topics like gender-related issues. This could lead to an underreporting of the actual challenges and biases faced by male students. The findings of the study may be specific to the context of Anambra State and may not be applicable to other regions or countries. The causes and solutions identified may

not be universally relevant. The study's findings are based on the situation at a particular point in time. Socioeconomic, political, and cultural factors influencing male enrollment in the Home Economics and related disciplines may change over time, and the solutions proposed may become outdated. The study may be limited in its ability to comprehensively investigate all the potential causes and solutions due to resource constraints, including time, funding, and access to data or participants. The study may not delve deeply into the cultural and societal norms that influence gender roles and expectations in Anambra State, which can play a crucial role in male student enrollment into Home Economics and related programmes. Further studies should conduct longitudinal studies to track changes in male enrollment over time. This can help identify trends, assess the effectiveness of implemented solutions, and understand how societal and institutional factors evolve. Studies are required to compare male enrollment in Home Economics with enrollment in other academic disciplines to identify factors specific to Home Economics that may be deterring male students. Comparative studies can reveal patterns and differences across departments. It is suggested to investigate specific tertiary institutions in Anambra State to understand how their individual policies, practices, and cultures impact male enrollment in the Home Economics department. This can help identify institution-specific issues and solutions. There is need to conduct surveys that focus on male students' and female students' perceptions of Home Economics and their reasons for enrolling or not enrolling. This comparative analysis can reveal gender-specific issues.

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study has explored the causes and potential solutions to the issue of poor male student enrollment in Home Economics departments within tertiary institutions in Anambra State, Nigeria. The findings have revealed several crucial insights that warrant attention and action. The causes of poor male student enrollment primarily revolve around societal stereotypes, misconceptions, and limited awareness of the subject's scope. Inadequate promotional efforts have contributed to the under representation of male students in Home Economics. The limited male participation in culinary arts within Home Economics calls for curriculum adjustments and a more inclusive educational environment, recognizing that culinary arts can be a field suitable for all students, regardless of gender. The study highlights the crucial role of the ministry of education in addressing gender bias through media campaigns and initiatives. Government support is essential to challenge traditional gender roles and promote equal participation in fields like Home Economics. These findings underscore the broader issue of gender equality in education, emphasizing the importance of creating educational environments that are inclusive and diverse. Encouraging male enrollment in Home Economics and related programs can expand career opportunities for both men and women in fields related to nutrition, food science, and household management. Addressing these challenges can have a positive economic and social impact, contributing to a more skilled workforce and improved family well-being, ultimately fostering a more inclusive and prosperous society.

Tertiary institutions in Anambra State should actively promote Home Economics and related programmes as gender-neutral. This can be achieved by revising promotional materials, organizing

awareness campaigns, and highlighting the career opportunities and benefits of studying Home Economics for both genders. The government should collaborate with curriculum planner's units to organize workshops and seminars in secondary schools to inform male students about the diverse career options and prospects in Home Economics. It is essential to challenge stereotypes and misconceptions about this field. The government should establish mentorship programs where current male students in Home Economics can serve as mentors for prospective students. They can share their experiences and successes, making the field more relatable and encouraging for potential male students. Government agencies and non-governmental organization (NGOs) should provide scholarships or financial incentives specifically targeted at male students interested in pursuing Home Economics and related programmes. These incentives can help alleviate the financial burden associated with tertiary education and make the program more attractive. Schools should conduct training sessions for faculty and staff members on gender sensitivity. Ensure that all students, regardless of their gender, feel welcome and supported in the department. Ministry of education should review the Home Economics curriculum to ensure that it includes a broader range of subjects and topics that appeal to male students.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors exhibited a high level of understanding and respect for individual differences; they share similar views about the topic.

Author Contributions

The study topic and design were conceived and developed by Cynthia Emeka. She also participated in the data collection, collation and analysis alongside the research colleague. Dr. Patricia Okoh conducted the reliability test as well as made reasonable contributions in data collection, collation and analysis.

Data Availability Statement

Primary data were used for this study and have not been made available on the internet.

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